

A Study on the Relationship between Job Satisfaction, Work Stress, and Mental Health among Corporate Employees

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The interrelationship between job satisfaction, work stress, and overall health plays a crucial role in shaping employees' well-being and organizational efficiency. Job satisfaction reflects one's emotional reaction towards their job, wrought by various aspects such as the work atmosphere, salary, and interpersonal connections. Work stress emerges from high job demands, conflicting roles, and a lack of control, which can result in burnout and decreased effectiveness. Physical and mental healths are impacted by job satisfaction and work stress, influencing the overall quality of life. The study aims to assess general health, work stress, and job satisfaction in the corporate sector. The study focuses on the well-being of employees of private domain. We focused on the sample for the corporate sector with a sample size of 100 employees; to assess the General Health Questionnaire (David Goldberg), the Work stress questionnaire revised version (Kristina Holmgren), and the Job Satisfaction Scale (Amar Singh & Sharma) were used. Recognizing these connections is essential for companies to foster a healthier and more efficient workforce. Contentment at work is a significant measure of an employee's well-being and productivity, with higher levels of satisfaction often linked to improved mental and physical health. Conversely, work-related stress can negatively impact health, leading to issues like burnout, anxiety, and decreased job performance. This paper explores the associations among work stress, job satisfaction, and mental health within industrial and organizational settings, emphasizing the importance of effective strategies to enhance employee well-being and productivity. All the hypotheses are accepted, and the result is significantly satisfactory. The study will help understand the healthy personnel and job satisfaction, followed by an overall understanding of their well-being.

Keywords: Industrial-organizational psychology, job satisfaction, mental health, work stress, job performance

In today's fast-paced and highly competitive workplace, the well-being of employees has become a vital element affecting both individual and organizational success. Work stress, job satisfaction and mental health are interconnected factors that affect workplace dynamics, influencing productivity, performance, engagement, and overall quality of life. While numerous studies have examined these elements in isolation, Comprehensive and integrated analysis remains necessary to understand their combined effects.

This research aims to investigate the complex relationships between work stress, job -satisfaction, and mental health, identifying key factors and outcomes within professional settings. By adding psychological, physiological, and organizational perspectives, this study try to finds to give a inclusive outline that enhances both academic insight and practical applications. Through this approach, we aim to facilitate the development of healthier, more fulfilling, and ultimately more sustainable work environments.

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Work Stress

Almost 50% of employees in India experience some form of stress (Bhattacharyya & Basu, 2018). Selye (1936) first described the concept of 'stress' as "a condition of mental and physical well-being resultant as of the unanticipated gap among demands and the inherent capabilities of an individual to respond, to meet those demands". The workplace today is fast-paced, has high levels of competition, and has many stresses for employees across industries and job roles. Due to these demanding work environments and pressures placed upon workers from outside the workplace. Therefore, it is no surprise that there is such an occurrence of stress among workers (Madhavi & Rao, 2023). Consequently, organisations want to maintain a motivated and productive workforce, thus they are concerned with understanding the effect of stress on employees' performance and level of job-satisfaction.

Stress at work reduces performance and has psychological consequences as well. Workplace stress raises the likelihood of physical injuries, depression, cardiovascular disease, high blood pressure and negative behaviors like anxiety and hostility (Kirkcaldy et al., 2002). It also promotes emotional fatigue (Kashif et al., 2017) reduce employee productivity (Pestonjee & Muncherji, 1991).

Manoj (2013) discovered that many firms' workplaces have become high-stress environments for their employees. High workloads, tight deadlines, unreasonable goals, a high level of job dissatisfaction, longer work hours, performance anxiety, and interactional problems are a numbers of the primary causes of stress among employees, which have an impact on worker productivity, motivation, and organizational profitability. Previous research finds

that the work environment, lack of organizational support, leads to occupation-related stress, which reduces employee performance (Osman et al., 2010; Tyagi & Pathak, 2014; Rosenbusch et al., 2015; Udod et al., 2017). Furthermore, Ray et al. (2017) that stressed individuals reported frequent absences from work owing to illness.

Job Satisfaction

It is a personnel attitude toward their employment, which is based on their viewpoint. While some people are unhappy with their occupations because of stress and pain at work, others love their jobs and give it their whole focus. A sense of work achievement and success at workplace is known as satisfaction of work/job. Job satisfaction is often supposed to be directly connected to equally well-being and work output. It also suggests passion and contentment with one's job. Recognition, pay, advancement, working conditions, and corporate culture all have an impact on this multifaceted construct (Kaliski, 2007).

In contrast, being dissatisfied at the workplace could hamper interest level, hamper productivity, absenteeism, even lead to job abandonment and cause negative effects of emotional health (Singh & Sabbarwal, 2019).

Workplace stress is widely recognized as a major factor affecting employee performance and job satisfaction. Madhavi and Srinivas (2023) highlight that high stress reduces productivity, increases errors and absenteeism, which leads to burnout and dissatisfaction, with key causes including heavy workloads, lack of control, poor work-life balance, and toxic environments. Researchers found that factors such as job uncertainty, low self-sufficiency, and demanding work conditions (Mujtaba et al., 2020) which contribute to job satisfaction, and job stress are key factors in an association that can influence its work production and performance (Hans et al., 2014). Overall, multiple studies have found that work stress is depressingly correlated with work satisfaction. Other factors that affect job satisfaction include working conditions, pay, promotional opportunities, job security, fairness in the workplace, and good relationships in the workplace (Bowling & Hammond, 2008; Lehal, 2007; Pravin & Kabir, 2011).

Mental Health

There is no such thing as mental health on its own. It is a key element of mental health, which can be depicted in these ways: as the good health, as an individual in a state that consents the overall performance, or as an equilibrium condition both within and between oneself as well as individual physical and social environment (Sartorius, 2002).

"Mental health is a state of mental well-being that enables people to cope with the stresses of life, realize their abilities, learn well and work well, and contribute to their community" (World Health Organization, 2022).

Stress that related with work can lead to mental health problems, which ultimately decrease people's overall quality of life and their working performance (Melchior et al., 2007 & Azzam et al., 2023). Additionally, a syndrome of work burnout is common among those who experience long-term work stress. It is distinguished by emotional depletion, depersonalization, and a lack of own achievement, especially in high-pressure job environments such as healthcare and education (Maslach et al., 2001). The demand-control-support framework presented by Karasek and Theorell

(1990) indicates that there are many ways in which a high-stress work environment causes long-term negative health consequences, including psychological problems (Chou et al., 2015; Park et al., 2016 & Lu et al., 2020). Stress is often defined through the DCS model's definition of work at excessive intensity and is expressed through cognitive, physical, emotional, and psychological stress (Houtman et al., 2007).

Workplace stress can lead to the following common signs of mental illness: irritability, anxiety, aggression, lack of focus, disruption to sleep patterns, and issues with memory (Neupane et al., 2017). Long-term exposure to workplace stress can also result in anxiety and depression over time (Eskilsson et al., 2017). The ongoing requirement to manage workplace stress on a continual basis by utilizing strategies for coping with that stress encompasses a large part of the association among stress and mental symptoms (Poms et al., 2016; Harrison & Stephens, 2019). When viewing mental health in the workplace, it is typically perceived as a measure of psychological distress, with an emphasis on symptoms of depression, anxiety, and social impairment.

Objective of the Study

The study aims to assess the relationship between work stress, job satisfaction, and mental health among employees in the corporate sector.

Hypotheses of the Study

- There will be a significant negative correlation between work stress and job satisfaction.
- There will be a significant negative correlation between job satisfaction and GHQ-a (Somatic symptoms).
- There will be a significant negative correlation between job satisfaction and GHQ-b (Anxiety & Insomnia).
- There will be a significant negative correlation between job satisfaction and GHQ-c (Social dysfunctions).
- There will be a significant negative correlation between job satisfaction and GHQ-d (Severe depression).
- There will be a significant negative correlation between job satisfaction and GHQ-t (Total GHQ Score).
- There will be a significant positive correlation between work stress and GHQ-a (Somatic symptoms).
- There will be a significant positive correlation between work stress and GHQ-b (Anxiety & Insomnia).
- There will be a significant positive correlation between work stress and GHQ-c (Social dysfunctions).
- There will be a significant positive correlation between work stress and GHQ-d (Severe depression).
- There will be a significant positive correlation between work stress and GHQ-t (Total GHQ Score).

Method

Participants

The present study included a sample of 100 employees ($N=100$), consisting of both males and females aged between 25 and 45 years. Data were collected through convenience sampling from different corporate sectors of North India. The study included only those individuals who had been working for more than two years to ensure adequate experience. Mode of data collection was offline and

online, offline data were collected using a paper-and-pencil format, while online data were collected through Google Forms. Before participation, all respondents were informed about the purpose of the study and informed consent were obtained.

Measures

General Health Questionnaire (GHQ-28): GHQ-28 (The General Health Questionnaire), created by Goldberg and Hillier in 1979, was exercised to determine the mental health of employees. The questionnaire had 28 items that were split into four groups: somatic symptoms (SS), anxiety and insomnia (AI), social dysfunction (SDys), and severe depression (SD). Respondents rated each item on a Likert scale, which showed how bad their symptoms had been in the past few weeks. The GHQ-28 was good at measuring current mental health by looking for changes in how well a person was functioning. The Likert method (0-1-2-3) was used to score, and higher scores meant more psychological distress. The range of total score is 0-84. The scale demonstrated high reliability with split-half reliability of 0.90, Cronbach's alpha was reported to range from 0.85 to .90. In this study, mental health was operationalized in terms of psychological distress, with higher GHQ-28 scores signifying worse mental health.

Job Satisfaction Scale (1986): Job Satisfaction Scale was constructed by Singh and Sharma (1986) to measure the job satisfaction level of a personnel. The scale had 30 statements, responded on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 0(not at all satisfied) to 4 (completely satisfied). The scale is divided into positive and negative statements, with higher scores indicating a higher level of job satisfaction. The minimum and maximum range of scores is 0-120. Reliability of test retest was reported to be 0.97.

Work Stress Questionnaire: Kristina Holmgren designed the Work Stress Questionnaire (WSQ) in 2008, which is a 21-item self-report

tool used to measure perceived work-related stress and early signs of stress-related health problems in employees. It had four parts: unclear workplace and conflicts, personal demands and dedication, control at work, and work leisure time interference. Items were rated on a Likert scale (1 - not at all to 4 - very much), with a total score range of 21 to 84. Higher scores indicate greater perceived work stress. The WSQ showed good to acceptable reliability, with Cronbach's alpha values usually between 0.70 and 0.86. It also demonstrated stable test-retest reliability, which makes it a good tool for research on occupational stress and employee well-being.

Procedure

In this study correlational design is used to study the relationship between work stress, job satisfaction and mental health. Before collecting data, a brief description of the study was given to the participants. After getting consent permission, the questionnaires were agreed to the participants in both online and offline ways. In the offline method, participants filled out the paper-and-pencil version of the questionnaire in a place that was quiet and free of distractions. For the online method, Google Forms was used to send out the questionnaire, so participants could answer it whenever they wanted. Participants received explicit instructions to respond to all items honestly and were guaranteed confidentiality and anonymity. Responses that were finished were gathered and checked to make sure they were complete. After that, the data were analysed using SPSS software.

Results

The current research was done to investigate the relationship between work stress, job satisfaction, and GHQ (Somatic symptoms, Anxiety and Insomnia, Social dysfunction, Severe depression) among corporate employees.

Table 1
Descriptive and Correlational Analysis

Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
JS	70.06	14.264	1	-.315**	-.584**	-.416**	-.464**	-.355**	-.539**
WS	26.20	8.777		1	.426**	.437**	.296**	.384**	.473**
GHQ-a	5.74	4.139			1	.714**	.389**	.519**	.802**
GHQ-b	5.99	5.076				1	.531**	.662**	.901**
GHQ-c	6.97	3.243					1	.580**	.721**
GHQ-d	4.15	4.976						1	.854**
GHQ-t	22.85	4.480							1

Note. ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). N=100 JS (Job Satisfaction), WS (Work Stress), GHQ-a (General Health Questionnaire- Somatic symptoms), GHQ-b (Anxiety & insomnia), GHQ-c (Social dysfunctions), GHQ-d (Severe depression), GHQ-t (Total score).

'Table 1' indicates the descriptive statistics along with the correlation analysis of all the selected variables. The results analysis revealed a correlation of work stress with job satisfaction ($r=-.315, p<0.01$). The outcomes of research show that work stress is significantly and negatively associated with job satisfaction. The correlation of job satisfaction with GHQ-a (Somatic symptoms) is ($r=-.584, p<0.01$). The results show that job satisfaction is significantly and negatively associated with GHQ-a. The correlation between job satisfaction and GHQ-b (Anxiety & insomnia) is ($r=-.416, p<0.01$), it shows that job satisfaction and GHQ-b are significantly and negatively associated.

The correlation between job satisfaction and GHQ-c (Social dysfunction) is ($r=-.464, p<0.01$). The results show that job satisfaction has a significant negative correlation with GHQ-c. The results analysis revealed a correlation of job satisfaction with GHQ-d (Severe depression) is ($r=-.355, p<0.01$). The results show that job satisfaction is significantly and negatively associated with GHQ-d. The correlation between job satisfaction and GHQ-t (GHQ total score) is ($r=-.539$), it shows that job satisfaction is significantly and negatively correlated with GHQ total score. The findings indicate a significant positive correlation between work stress and GHQ-a

($r=.426$, $p<0.01$). Similarly, job satisfaction shows a significant positive correlation with GHQ-b ($r=.437$). A significant positive correlation is also observed between work stress and GHQ-c ($r=.296$, $p<0.01$). Furthermore, work stress is positively correlated with GHQ-d ($r=.384$, $p<0.01$), and overall, work stress demonstrates a strong positive correlation with the GHQ total score ($r=.473$, $p<0.01$).

Discussion

The present research work intends to study the association between work stress, job satisfaction, and general mental health, including its subdimensions: (GHQ-a) Somatic symptoms, (GHQ-b) Anxiety and Insomnia, (GHQ-c) Social dysfunction, and (GHQ-d) Severe depression, among employees in the corporate sector. Hypothesis (a) states that there will be a significant negative correlation between work stress and job satisfaction, which indicates that individuals with less job stress have better job satisfaction. The Job Demands-Resources model proposed by Bakker and Demerouti (2007) explains that excessive job demands deplete individual resources, resulting in burnout and reduced job satisfaction. The outcomes of current research are consistent with previous studies, which conclude that job stress arising from workload, job insecurity, and work-life imbalance consistently leads to decreased job satisfaction across occupations (Dey & Bhattacharjee, 2025). Burnout and job stress reduce job satisfaction among health care workers (Çivilidağ et al., 2024). Therefore, integrating both classical theories and recent empirical reviews, it can be concluded that individuals experiencing lower work stress are more likely to report higher job satisfaction.

The hypothesis-II states that there will be a significant negative correlation between job satisfaction and GHQ-a (Somatic symptoms), which was also accepted. In line with previous research, job satisfaction is a key determinant of employee well-being, with lower satisfaction linked to poorer health outcomes and higher levels of strain-related symptoms (Spector, 1997; Thielmann et al., 2023). It can be concluded that lower job satisfaction is associated with higher levels of somatic symptoms, as measured by GHQ-a. The hypothesis (c) was accepted, which claimed that job satisfaction was negatively correlated with GHQ-b (Anxiety & Insomnia). The result of the current study was in line with preceding research, indicating that work-related stressors are consistently connected with poor sleep quality and increased psychological distress, including anxiety symptoms across occupational groups (Mao et al., 2023). Insomnia in workers is strongly associated with dissatisfaction and poor work conditions (Engelbrecht et al., 2026) anxiety, fatigue, and impaired psychological well-being, reinforcing the close interconnection between sleep disturbances and anxiety outcomes (Takano et al., 2023). Collectively, these recent reviews suggest that unfavorable work experiences, reflected in low job satisfaction, are associated with increased anxiety and insomnia.

The hypothesis (d) was accepted, which claimed that job satisfaction was negatively associated with GHQ-c (Social dysfunctions). According to previous literature, job satisfaction is essential for an employee's psycho-social performance. Recent reviews (Bhoir & Sinha, 2024) have continued to confirm that individuals with low levels of job satisfaction have demonstrated poor social performance, including decreased effectiveness in social interactions, social isolation, and challenges executing their specific roles. Furthermore, research studies (Spector, 1997; Karasek, 1979) have found that low job satisfaction is linked to poor social function

overall. Therefore, job satisfaction will be negatively correlated with social dysfunction as measured via the GHQ-c. Results indicate a positive correlation between job satisfaction and mental wellness. For all occupational groups, low job satisfaction is linked to high levels of psychological distress and depression symptoms, according to numerous comprehensive research studies. Negative working conditions and job dissatisfaction have been linked to the development of depressive disorder (Wahrendorf & Siegrist, 2023). Lower job satisfaction and the psychosocial work environment are predictors of developing depression (Stansfeld & Candy, 2006). This review line up with the hypothesis (e), which proposed a significant negative correlation between job satisfaction and GHQ-d (Severe depression).

The hypothesis (f) stated that job satisfaction will negatively correlate with total GHQ score (GHQ-t). Existing research indicates that work satisfaction is a major factor in determining an individual's overall psychological well-being, as data are showing lower levels of work satisfaction correspond to high levels of general psychological illness, such as anxiety and depression (Haar et al., 2014; Davood & Tayebbeh, 2012; Siegrist, 1996). The data support the hypothesis predicting that a negative correlation between satisfaction at work and overall mental health exists.

The seventh hypothesis (g) states that there will be a significant positive correlation between work stress and GHQ-a (Somatic symptoms), which was also accepted. Consistent with prior studies, Higher rates of heart problems, depression, emotional disturbances, impaired immune system, burnout, and somatic problems are the result of workplace stress (Naeem et al.). According to the demand-control model, stress is a person's reaction to a perceived heavy workload, which alters an employee's mental, emotional, physical, and cognitive state (Houtman et al., 2007). Therefore, higher levels of somatic issues are linked to increasing work stress.

The eighth hypothesis (h) states that stress at work will be significantly positively correlated with GHQ-b (Anxiety & insomnia), which was supported. Recent research indicates that sleep disturbances are common in working-age populations, with a reciprocal connection between sleep quality and occupational factors (Linton & Bryngelsson, 2002). Work-related stress factors like workplace pressure, lack of decision-making power, poor support, high mental pressure, less rewards, and low job security were found to contribute to occupational stress, depression, and anxiety (Stansfeld & Candy, 2006). The results of this study were in line with other studies, that the stress arising from heavy workload, organizational culture, and job insecurity is connected to higher levels of anxiety and sleep issues.

The ninth hypothesis (I) was accepted, which claimed that work stress was positively associated with GHQ-c (Social dysfunctions). Latest investigations find that significant associations between work-related psychosocial stress (e.g., occupational pressure, high efforts-low reward) and depression, which often manifests as social withdrawal and dysfunction (Dragano et al., 2024). The tenth (j) hypothesis, which was verified, predicts a substantial relationship between GHQ-d (severe depression) and work stress. A one-way ANOVA of 337 workers revealed that the levels of job-related stress in public and private sector banks differ. According to George and K.A. (2015), job stress in an organization can lead to melancholy, low self-esteem, decreased interest in work, decreased performance capacity, and decreased efficiency. Workplace stress frequently results in mental health difficulties, such as irritability, anxiety,

aggressive behavior, inattention, sleep disruptions, and memory disorders (Mayerl et al., 2016; Neupane & Nygard, 2017).

The tenth (j) hypothesis suggests that there will be a significant association between work stress and GHQ-d (Severe depression), which was confirmed. Research indicated that both public and private sector banks have different levels of work place stress after performance a one-way ANOVA of 337 employees. Job stress in an organization can decrease performance ability, reduce efficiency, cause depression, low self-esteem, and reduce interest in work (George & K.A., 2015). Mental health issues, irritability, anxiety, aggressive behaviour, inattention, sleep disturbances, and memory problems, are common responses to work stress (Neupane & Nygard, 2017). Mental health issues like anxiety or sadness may arise if this reaction persists for a long time (Eskilsson et al., 2017). Therefore, higher levels of depression and social dysfunctions are linked to increasing work stress.

Existing research indicates that occupational stress negatively correlates with the overall well-being of employees and reduced psychopathology symptoms (anxiety/depression) among employees (Forbes et al., 2020). In a large cohort of workers, the onset of job stress in terms of high effort and low reward is linked to an increased risk of poor mental health (Godin et al., 2005). The hypothesis (k), which suggested a strong positive association between work stress and GHQ total score, is supported by this review. In conclusion, poorer mental health was associated with higher levels of work-related stress.

Limitation and Future Directions

The present research will help administrators, policymakers, and employees improve their knowledge and understanding of the workplace and mental health. This study provides essential information into the relationships between work stress, job discontent, and mental health. However, the current study has a limited sample size; in the future, with a larger sample size, these variables can be investigated for improved generalization.

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